

Synthesis of Mannich Bases from Methyl 7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate as Possible Nervous System Stimulants

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In continuation of our previous work^{1,2} on the Mannich bases from coumarin derivatives, a few more Mannich bases from methyl 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate have been described in the present communication. This coumarin was prepared by condensing methyl β -resorcyate with ethyl acetoacetate³. The coumarin, when condensed in absolute ethanol with paraformaldehyde and different secondary amines (Table I), provides the corresponding Mannich bases. The products isolated as hydrochlorides are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

N-Substituted methyl 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-8-aminomethylcoumarin-6-carboxylate hydrochlorides.

R.	Formula.	*M.P.	%Yield.	%Nitrogen.		%Chlorine.	
				Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
NMe ₂	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ O ₅ NCl	208°	40	4.20	4.27	10.61	10.83
NEt ₂	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ O ₅ NCl	300°	62	3.81	3.93	9.82	9.98
NPr ₂	C ₁₉ H ₂₆ O ₅ NCl	> 134°	48	3.52	3.65	9.28	9.25
NBu ₂	C ₂₁ H ₃₀ O ₅ NCl	135°	42	3.42	3.40	8.51	8.62
N-isoBu ₂	C ₂₁ H ₃₀ O ₅ NCl	137°	38	3.46	3.40	8.70	8.62
N-isoAm ₂	C ₂₃ H ₃₄ O ₅ NCl	138°	30	3.29	3.18	8.21	8.07
N(C ₂ H ₄ OH) ₂	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ O ₇ NCl	148-50°	65	3.48	3.61	9.22	9.16
N(PhCH ₂) ₂	C ₂₇ H ₂₆ O ₅ NCl	200°	70	2.85	2.91	7.28	7.40
N(C ₃ H ₇) ₂	C ₁₈ H ₂₆ O ₅ NCl	218°	58	3.63	3.80	9.55	9.65
N(C ₄ H ₉ O)	C ₁₇ H ₂₆ O ₆ NCl	204°	55	3.59	3.78	9.72	9.60
N(C ₄ H ₉) ₂	C ₁₇ H ₂₆ O ₅ NCl	240°	50	4.12	3.98	10.26	10.04
	C ₁₈ H ₂₅ O ₅ N ₂ Cl	220°	30	7.00	7.32	9.14	9.28

*All m.p.s are uncorrected.

1. Kumar and Joshi, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1963, 26, 149.
2. *Idem*, this *Journal*, 1964, 41, 200.
3. Shah *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1937, 14, 717.

General Procedure for the Mannich Reaction.—A mixture of methyl 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate (0.01*M*), paraformaldehyde (0.01*M*), and the secondary amine (0.01*M*) in absolute ethanol was refluxed on a steam bath for 10 hr. After cooling, the mixture was acidified with ethanolic HCl. The hydrochloride separating on concentration and cooling was crystallised from ethanol.

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